

A RARE CASE OF CHRONIC PANCREATITIS COMPLICATED BY INTERNAL PANCREATIC FISTULA AND PANCREATOGENIC ASCITES

Andrey Kriger^{*,1}, David Gorin^{*}, Ayrat R. Kaldarov^{*}, Stanislav Berelavichus^{*}, Gleb Galkin^{*}, Valeriya Pletneva^{*} and Grigoriy Karmazanovsky^{*}

^{*}A.V. Vishnevsky Institute of Surgery, Ministry of Health, 27 Bolshaya Serpuhovskaja str., Moscow, 115093, Russian Federation.

ABSTRACT

Objective: pancreatogenic ascites is a rare complication of chronic pancreatitis associated with a rupture in the ductal system and caused by an internal pancreatic fistula. It can become as a result of chronic pancreatitis, injury of the pancreas and stricture of the pancreatic duct. **Case presentation:** 40 years old male was admitted to our hospital suffered from surrounded epigastric pain, nausea, vomiting, enlargement of the abdomen, dyspnoea. Anamnesis showed that patient suffers from chronic calculous pancreatitis for four years, was hospitalised 8-9 times per year for conservative treatment. The patient was admitted to our clinic in medium severity condition. Laparocentesis with the fluid examination revealed amylase level 6007 U/L, protein 3.8 g/L. CT scan showed multiple calcifications in the pancreatic parenchyma, pancreatic duct dilation to 5 - 7 mm, large concretions (5-6 mm) in the pancreatic duct, postnecrotic cyst 34 mm diameter in the pancreatic head, smaller cyst 23 mm diameter in the pancreatic body from which, most likely, proceed pancreatic fistula. The patient was operated. The cystopancreatojejunostomy with dissection of the fistula was performed. The patient returned three months later with recurrent complaints of pain and increasing of the abdomen due to the fluid component. According to preoperative examinations (CT), it seemed like the recurrence of internal pancreatic fistula. Amylase level of the fluid was 22 U/L, protein level 41 g/L. Nevertheless, considering the chronic calculous pancreatitis surgical treatment was performed: subtotal pancreatic head resection with reconstruction of the pancreatojejunostomosis. **Conclusion:** internal pancreatic fistula with the pancreatogenic ascites is a rare complication of chronic pancreatitis. In cases, without any other significant changes (pseudocysts, pancreatic duct dilation, calculus) it can be treated by endoscopic stent placement. Surgical treatment is prior in complicated cases. The surgical approach does not always have a positive result because of inflammatory infiltration.

KEYWORDS pancreatogenic ascites, pancreatic fistula, internal pancreatic fistula, chronic pancreatitis.

INTRODUCTION

Pancreatogenic ascites is a rare complication of chronic pancreatitis and frequently associated with a rupture in the ductal system of the pancreas that opening to the abdominal cavity, i.e. internal pancreatic fistula. Pancreatogenic ascites can become as a result of chronic pancreatitis, injury of the pancreas and stricture of the pancreatic duct [1]. For the last ten years, a few scientific works about the diagnostic and treatment of the patients with the pancreatogenic ascites have been published [2-7]. In 2003 J.

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¹Kaldarov Ayrat Radikovich 27 B. Serpuhovskaja Street Moscow, 115093, Russian Federation; ayratikus@gmail.com

Figure 1: CT scan, frontal imagine, arterial phase. CT shows the pseudocyst of the pancreatic head with many concrements in the pancreatic parenchyma and pancreatic hypertension.

Figure 2: CT scan, axial imagine, portal phase. The narrow shows recurrence of pancreatic hypertension which signs an inadequate functioning of the primary anastomosis.

Gomez-Cerezo et al. reviewed world literature from 1975 to 2000 [8]. During this period 139 observations were published. Due to the lack of randomised studies, there is no unified treatment strategy for this category of the patients. In abdominal surgery department of A. V. Vishnevsky Institute of Surgery 670 patients with chronic pancreatitis was treated between 2000 and 2013; in 7 cases it was complicated by the pancreatogenic ascites.

CASE REPORT

Patient O., 40 years old was admitted to our hospital at 26.02.2014 suffered from surrounded epigastric pain, nausea, vomiting, enlargement of the abdomen, dyspnoea. Anamnesis showed that patient suffers from chronic calculous pancreatitis for four years, frequently was admitted to the hospitals. Since December 2013 dyspnoea, enlargement of the abdomen appeared. In January 2014 he was admitted to the hospital at the place of residence with these complaints. Laparocentesis was performed, and 12 litres of fluid was evacuated. Cytology was not performed, and the level of amylase was not identified. Tumour markers were normal. Cause of ascites was not determined.

The patient was admitted to our hospital with common severity condition. He was cachectic with BMI 16.8 kg/m². Weight loss for the last six months was 32%. Hypoderm was practically lacked. Abdomen size was increased due to the liquid. At palpation, the abdomen was soft and painful in the epigastrium

and the left hypochondrium. Palpation was uninformative due in no small amount of liquid in the abdominal cavity. Analysis results showed anaemia, hypoproteinemia and electrolyte insufficiency.

Laparocentesis with the fluid examination revealed amylase level 6007 U/L, protein 3.8 g/L, atypical cells were not revealed. CT scan showed: multiple calcifications in the pancreatic parenchyma, pancreatic duct dilation to 5 - 7 mm, large concrements (5-6 mm) were in the pancreatic duct, postnecrotic cyst 34 mm diameter was in the pancreatic head, smaller cyst 23 mm diameter was in the pancreatic body from which, most likely, proceed with pancreatic fistula (fig. 1). Based on these data diagnosis of chronic pancreatitis, pancreatic hypertension, internal pancreatic fistula, pancreatic ascites was determined.

Preoperatively patient received intensive parenteral and enteral nutrition for 14 days. Laparocentesis was performed twice, and 2,5 litres and 3 litres of fluid were evacuated. The patient's body weight increased by 5 kg after preparation.

11.03.2014 patient was operated. The transverse laparotomy was performed. 5 litres of transparent liquid fluid was evacuated from the abdominal cavity. The peritoneum was hyperemic, without fibrous depositions. The omentum was infiltrated in the place of the middle third of the stomach and transverse colon. When the inflammatory mass was separated from the parietal peritoneum pancreatic fluid leakage started. This made possible to detect the pancreatic fistula which arose from the pancreatic body. The pancreatic head was enlarged to 6-7 sm and involved into an inflammatory infiltrate so tissues could not be identified.

The cystic cavity in the area of the pancreatic body with previously detected pancreatic fistula was dissected among the fistula. Size of dissected cyst 3-4 cm. Pancreatic duct was opened from the cyst until the pancreatic tail. There were not any strictures and concrements. Than pancreatic duct was dissected from the body till the pancreatic head cyst, the necrotic mass was extracted. The further surgical situation of pancreatic head infiltration resection was inappropriate and dangerous. The cystopancreatojejunostomy was performed. One silicon drainage was placed. There were no complications after surgery. Drainage outflow was less than 300 ml per day without any amylase level. On the 5th day after surgery drainage was removed. The patient was discharged from the hospital on the 8th day after the operation without any complaints.

The patient returned to our hospital three months later with recurrent complaints of pain and increasing of the abdomen due to the fluid component. According to preoperative examinations (CT), it seemed like the recurrence of internal pancreatic fistula. MRI and MRCP scans were not informative (fig. 2). Amylase level of the fluid was 22 U/L, protein level 41 g/L, the oncomarkers status was negative.

Nevertheless, considering the chronic calculous pancreatitis with pancreatic hypertension and the pain syndrome we decided to perform a surgical treatment. 30.07.2017 subtotal pancreatic head resection with reconstruction of the pancreatojejunostomosis (Bern procedure) was performed [9]. Intraoperative: previously formed cystopancreatojejunostomosis was visualised. The anastomosis was dissected, its length about 5 cm, anastomotic cavity communicated with the pancreatic duct with a narrow channel, less than 3 mm, drainage function of the anastomosis was inadequate. The pancreatic head was solid structure and enlarged in sizes up to 5 cm. The duct was dissected longitudinally with dissection of the strictures; concrements were removed (3-6 mm). Subtotal resection of the pancreatic head was

performed, thin strip of parenchyma along the duodenum was left. The common bile duct was opened into the crater. Longitudinal pancreatojejunostomy was performed on the Roux loop side by side with a single-row continuous suture. Postoperative recovery was unremarkable. The patient was discharged from the clinic on the 7th day after the operation. Three years follow-up did not reveal the recurrence of pancreatogenic ascites or signs of chronic pancreatitis. CT scans showed no specific signs or complications of chronic pancreatitis. Now it's outpatient follow-up still performed.

DISCUSSION

Pancreatogenic ascites is a result of non-tumorous pancreatic disease and characterised by an amylase level more than 1000 U/l and a protein level of at least 3 g/l [1,3-5,10]. The first report about internal pancreatic fistulas in 2 patients with chronic pancreatitis complicated by pancreatogenic ascites was published in 1953 [1,11,12]. In 43-80% of cases, the genesis of pancreatogenic ascites is associated with the pancreatic fluid leakage through the rupture of the postnecrotic cyst, in 10% of cases - through the defect of the pancreatic duct. In 10% of patients, the cause of ascites is undefined [10,13-16]. J. Cameron et al. described 85 patients with pancreatogenic ascites, which caused by chronic pancreatitis (77.6%), traumatic pancreatic injury (8.4%), stenosis of the pancreatic duct (4%). In 10% of cases, the cause of ascites is undefined [3-5].

Pancreatogenic ascites is more common in male cases 46-57 years [10]. Clinical manifestations consist of a body weight loss with a significant increase in the abdominal size, abdominal pain of varying intensity [17]. The absence of peritoneal symptoms in the presence of a pancreatogenic fluid in the abdominal cavity is associated with the inactivation of pancreatic enzymes in the abdominal cavity [1,18,19]. Due to excretory insufficiency, malabsorption, hypoproteinemia and elementary dysbalance develop which leads to exhaustion, disturbance of homeostasis [20].

Diagnostic search should take place in three directions: assessment of the condition of the patient and nutritional status; specification of the cause of ascites; visualisation of the pancreatic duct to clarify the possible defect [3-5,10,21]. Laparocentesis with an amylase and protein analysis of the fluid should be performed to explain the cause of ascites. The pancreatic duct defect visualisation is an essential diagnostic component and plays a role in the surgical intervention planning. Combination of radiological methods (casually CT + MRCP) makes possible to visualise the internal pancreatic fistula with a probability up to 94% [22-24].

Treating patients with pancreatic fistula and pancreatogenic ascites is a complex problem. In high-volume pancreatic centres it is possible to use endoscopic technologies to repair the pancreatic fistula. The pancreatic duct stenting can have a positive effect without performing an operative intervention [7,15,25]. However, in this case, we decided to perform a pancreatic resection due to other signs of chronic pancreatitis (postnecrotic cysts and concrements), which in any case would require surgery [26-28].

CONCLUSION

Pancreatogenic ascites with the internal pancreatic fistula is a rare complication of chronic pancreatitis. There is still no universal treatment conception. It can be treated with pancreatic

duct stenting. Surgery is the way to choose if there are other complications of chronic pancreatitis. Only pancreatic resection with adequate drainage of the pancreatic duct can help to avoid the recurrence of the disease.

PATIENT CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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